

AI-Powered Diagnosis and Disease Management System

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Abstract. This system takes symptoms as input and provides a diagnosis as output. It also assists in chronic disease prevention and can guide individuals with chronic conditions. Users can read health-related articles as well. The system is designed for anyone who wants to identify potential health issues early. The interaction between the system and users is efficient and effective. Additionally, it serves as a platform for sharing knowledge and literature. Being a web-based system accessible on any device, it is user- friendly and available to everyone. Therefore, it is not limited to specific users or occasional use but is a system that can be utilized whenever needed.

Keywords: disease, diagnosis, health, prevention, symptoms.

INTRODUCTION

As long as there is a body, illnesses and ailments are inevitable. When sickness is occurred, early detection is crucial. Diseases manifest through symptoms unless one is a doctor, most people cannot determine the underlying cause of these symptoms. During times when visiting a doctor is difficult or not yet possible, this system can be used to understand potential illnesses, much like getting an explanation from a doctor. Additionally, the system serves two purposes for chronic diseases another major health concern: prevention from chronic disease and managing chronic conditions in order to prevent worsening. The prevention aspect follows a question-and-answer format, where the system asks symptoms and the user responds. This helps the users learn about diseases and identify lifestyle weaknesses. Moreover, the users can write and read health articles, similar to posting on social media. This feature promotes knowledge-sharing and awareness of diseases in an accessible way.

PROBLEM

In today's fast-paced world, people are increasingly busy, often neglecting their health. Even when experiencing symptoms like dizziness, they tend to ignore them rather than investigating the underlying cause. This leads to worsening health conditions over time. Additionally, while health awareness exists, access to reliable information remains limited. Discussions about health are rare in everyday conversations, leaving many

unaware of preventive measures. The saying "prevention is better than cure" is widely known, yet people lack precise knowledge on how to maintain a disease-free lifestyle. Moreover, patients oftentimes themselves to just taking medication without adjusting their daily habits for better health management. To address these issues, this system is developed with the goal of promoting proactive health awareness, early diagnosis, and proper disease management.

APPROACH

This system consists of three types of actors: Admin, User, and Visitor. Each has different levels of access and functionality. As an admin, the admin has the highest level of control over the system. Admin can monitor and manage the entire system and can edit records and moderate content. Admin has the authority to suspend or restrict malicious users. As a user, the user can diagnose diseases based on symptoms, access the chronic disease management system to track and improve health habits, read and write health articles, post comments on articles for discussions. As a visitor, the visitor can use the chronic disease lifestyle management system, read health articles but cannot write or post them and cannot comment on articles (requires registration/login). This structured approach ensures secure, efficient, and role-based access, enhancing usability while maintaining system integrity.

Figure 1: System Flow Diagram

Figure 2: Database Design

An Entity Relationship Diagram (ERD) uses data modeling techniques to define business processes and serves as a foundation for designing a relational database. In an ERD, an attribute can be designated as a primary key, which uniquely identifies each record in an entity, or as a foreign key, which establishes a link between entities by referencing the primary key in another entity. Additionally, cardinality notation is used to define the numerical relationships between entities, specifying how many instances of one entity can be associated with instances of another. In the database, there are six data tables for administrator and user. The tables are users, diagnosis_disease, article, chronic_disease, comment_to_article and comment_to_comment. The figure 2 shows database design for all the data tables and their relationship of the database.

RESULTS

This system enables early detection of diseases. The patient can get accurate results instantly ask now and know immediately. It provides a thorough understanding of various diseases. The system has the best user interaction and communication. It offers excellent and effective support for chronic disease prevention and management. The patient can gain extensive health knowledge. The learning resources are comprehensive. It is user-friendly

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and easy to use, with fast response times. With strong web security, the patient's data is protected and reliable. The patient can use it anytime, anywhere, for the long term.

Figure 3: Home Page

Figure 4: System Report

CONCLUSION

This system serves as an innovative and accessible health solution, bridging the gap between symptom recognition and early diagnosis. By allowing the users to input symptoms and receive instant, reliable diagnoses, it empowers individuals to take proactive steps in understanding their health. Additionally, the system promotes health literacy through interactive Q&A formats and a knowledge-sharing platform where users can read and contribute health-related articles. In the world where busy lifestyles often lead to neglected health, this system acts as a vital tool for early detection, disease prevention, and long-term wellness. By fostering awareness and encouraging better health practices, it helps the users make informed decisions, ultimately contributing to improve the public health outcomes.

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